

Tingui: the sickness by exposure to marine aerosols in the Northeast of Brazil

Fig. 1. Map of Brazil showing the municipalities of Recife, Tamandaré, Barra de São Miguel, Lagoa Azeda, and Porto Seguro in Northeast Brazil.

In Tamandaré Bay ($8^{\circ}47'20''$ S, $35^{\circ}06'45''$ W, Fig. 1), on the northeastern coast of Brazil, a peculiar toxic event occurs in which people exposed to marine aerosols become ill. Symptoms begin with respiratory problems (runny nose, sneezing), epistaxis, eye irritation, cough, and asthenia, progressing to fever, muscle, joint, and post-orbital pain. Some patients may experience gastrointestinal symptoms, and in a few cases, the illness may lead to depression and drowsiness [1]. These events were first reported by physician Frederico Barbosa, who called the condition

“Tamandaré fever” in the summer of 1943, when hundreds of soldiers from a military base near the beach fell ill with *tingui*, a syndrome well known to the local community at that time. Tingui is a word from the Tupi language group that may have different etymologies [1]. The ancient Tupi word “*tingy*” or “*tingyry*” means “*seasickness liquid*” [2], while the word “*tinguy*” refers to a plant from the Sapindaceae family used to poison freshwater fish but considered harmless to humans [3]. Other possible etymologies for the word refer to foam or foamy water [4].

Tingui occurs during summer and affects people close to the seashore for two to three days. It is often characterized by an unpleasant odour from the sea and may or may not be accompanied by red discolorations and foam in seawater [1, 5]. Satô et al. [5] interviewed the local community of Tamandaré in 1963 and documented strong tingui events in the summers of 1955 and 1958, although no reports of red or discoloured waters were mentioned. In 1961, red discoloration was reported without a tingui event, and in 1963, red stains in seawater were linked to tingui, accompanied by an unpleasant odour in the air. The authors speculated that tingui might be caused by aerosols containing fragments or intracellular contents of *Trichodesmium erythraeum* Ehrenberg ex Gomont cells, drawing comparisons with reports of respiratory distress and other symptoms caused by exposure to aerosols during blooms of *Karenia* (then identified as *Gymnodinium*) in Venice Beach, Florida. Satô et al. [5] did not examine seawater samples from Tamandaré during the 1963 tingui event, but extensively studied a *T. erythraeum* bloom in the city of Recife, 120 km north of Tamandaré, during the same period (October 1963). In Recife, no tingui related symptoms were observed during the *T. erythraeum* bloom.

No studies have addressed the tingui since then, despite continued occurrences. In 2017, a long-term ecological research programme, “Tamandaré Sustentável” (PELD TAMS-ILTER site 18) was initiated at Tamandaré Bay, including phytoplankton monitoring. In

Fig. 2. Images of tingui occurrences in Tamandaré in April and May 2023, showing (A) foam and (B) an oily appearance in the water column without visible stains. Source: Thales Vidal e Mauro Maida (2023).

Fig. 3. (A) Coastal area and cliffs of Lagoa Azeda, also known as Lagoa de Jequiá da Praia, in Alagoas. (B) Temporary houses for residents, known as “ranchos,” used during the tingui period in the municipality. Source: Alagoas Mapa (2022).

May 2023, during a tingui event when foam and “oily” seawater were noticed (Fig. 2), a dinoflagellate species (not identified) was present in high abundances in water samples collected during the event. On 31 January 2024, a very intense tingui event led 338 people to seek medical assistance [6]. This number is likely underreported, as many residents and tourists are accustomed to tingui symptoms and do not seek medical care. No water discoloration was observed during this event, either from the seashore or in satellite images. On 1 February 2024, 191 people were admitted to a health unit at Barra de Santo Antônio, 80 km south of Tamandaré, with nausea, sore throat, stomach pain, cough, runny nose, nasal obstruction, and signs of conjunctivitis, after exposure to marine aerosols [7]. Water samples collected in 2024 from Tamandaré presented low phytoplankton abundance and only a few diatom species identified.

Tingui is also known to occur in Lagoa Azeda, a small fishing village, located between the sea and the cliffs (Fig. 3A), 170 km south from Tamandaré in the state of Alagoas. There, the phenomenon is well known by the local community, and residents experience symptoms such as sore throat, shortness of breath, sneezing, intense body pain, and fever. To avoid illness from marine aerosol exposure, the community moves to houses uphill (Fig. 3B), specifically built for this purpose. These houses, known as “ranchos”, accommodate fishermen’s families during these events, which last on average three days. The local population does not seek medical care, as they are ac-

customed to the symptoms. According to fishermen, there is an unpleasant odour that quickly affects people, triggering flu-like symptoms, and recovery takes two to three days. Fishermen also report that calm seas and “oily” seawater often precede intoxication events.

Studies on the species responsible for tingui and the conditions that lead to human symptoms remain scarce. However, awareness of these events and their potential consequences for human health and economic activities in these touristic areas is increasing. There is also a perception that these phenomena have become more frequent and intense in recent years, possibly due to regional environmental changes such as rising temperature anomalies associated with climate change and increased land-based discharges. During the summer, the population of Tamandaré city increases significantly due to tourism, leading to greater sewage discharge and eutrophication of coastal waters.

In upcoming summers, phytoplankton and benthic microalgae monitoring, along with documentation of tingui events, is planned under the PELD TAMS project to investigate the toxic microalgae potentially involved in these intoxications. Meanwhile, communication efforts with local environmental and health authorities, as well as residents and fishermen, are being implemented to raise awareness about tingui and establish an integrated network of individuals engaged in understanding its causes.

Acknowledgements

We thank CAPES for the doctoral schol-

arship to Marcella Guennes (88887.633847/2021-00) and CNPq for financing the PELD Tamandaré project (442139/2020-9).

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14883687>